

Electronic and morphological properties of the graphene/Ge(110) interface as a function of temperature

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1. Introduction

Graphene gives rise to many unique properties and device concepts, with transformational opportunities for integrated solid state device technology [1]. In this contest a viable growth route for obtaining metal-free, CMOS-compatible graphene suitable for electronic and optoelectronics applications is the CVD graphene on Ge system. Indeed, thanks to the catalytic activity of Ge on carbon precursors combined with Ge carbides instability, and low C solubility, the controlled synthesis of graphene on the Ge surface is allowed [2]. Initially, most of the attention has been focused on the technologically relevant Ge(001) surface. However the development during the growth of Ge(001) nanofaceting under the graphene [3-4] questioned its suitability for technological processing, and has led to interest in graphene/Ge(110) for which the underlying Ge surface not only remains flat but also promotes the formation of a graphene single crystal. The data reported in literature reveal a complex scenario for the graphene/Ge(110) interface properties depending on hydrogen presence and annealing temperature, questioning a possible interaction between graphene and Ge surface [5-7]. However, a clear picture of the graphene/Ge(100) interface properties is still lacking. In this work we will investigate in detail the role of the growth and annealing temperatures on the properties of the graphene/Ge(110) system.

2. Results and discussion

The graphene films on Ge(110) substrate were deposited by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) using methane, hydrogen and Ar as carrier gas. Deposition temperature was set in the 910 - 930 °C range using a raising procedure that ensures an accurate control of temperature close to the Ge melting. Post growth annealing up to 800 °C were performed in UHV. The samples were characterized by X-ray, angle resolved photoemission spectroscopy (ARPES) and Raman spectroscopy, atomic force microscopy (AFM) and

scanning tunneling microscopy (STM).

We investigated the role of the deposition temperature T_D on the graphene quality by depositing samples at T_D equal to 910, 920 and 930 °C for a deposition time of 60 min. All the samples are single layer graphene: we found that the total amount of carbon did not depend significantly on the T_D in this range explored [8]. Raman spectra, AFM and STM images of the three samples are reported in Fig. 1. The small variation of the growth temperature has a significant effect on the quality of the grown graphene. In all the samples Raman spectra (panel a) show the features of graphene, i.e. 2D and G bands respectively at about 2700 and 1600 cm^{-1} . The D peak originating from the scattering due to defects is also visible. At the higher T_D we observe the larger I_{2D}/I_G and lower I_D/I_G intensity ratios. These findings evidence as in this temperature range an increase of T_D as low as 20 °C produces a major improvement in the crystalline quality, and it is also effective in the reduction of the defect density in the as-grown graphene sample. AFM and STM images of the three samples (panels b-d) reveal that also the morphology changes dramatically. AFM measurements acquired at large size scale evidence the presence of the Ge terraces in all the samples but their width increases remarkably with T_D , from being <70 nm at 910 °C to be larger than hundreds of nm at 930 °C. At higher magnification, STM data reveal that in all the samples graphene covers uniformly the Ge surface following the corrugation of the substrate surface. In the samples grown for T_D below 930 °C ridges and round bumps are present; graphene became flat in the sample grown at 930 °C that shows a rms roughness of 0.21 Å, a value half of that found at lower T_D . We attribute this abrupt temperature dependence to the formation of a quasi-liquid Ge surface that favors the formation of high quality graphene, through a mechanism observed also on the graphene/Ge(100) system [8]. We investigate the graphene/Ge(110) interface properties of the best quality sample (i.e the sample deposited at $T_D=930$ °C) by performing post-growth

annealing at different temperature T . The annealing temperature affects both the graphene quality and interface characteristics, as shown in Fig. 2: by rising T up to 800 °C three different phases appear characterized by different Ge surface reconstruction underneath the graphene layer and different graphene electronic properties. For T below 350 °C the hydrogenated Ge(110) surface shows a 1x1 reconstruction. ARPES measurements reveal that the graphene overlayer is p doped. The corresponding Raman spectrum is similar to that of the as-grown sample. The T increase above 350 °C produces the hydrogen desorption from the Ge surface meanwhile novel (6x2) Ge surface reconstruction is detected by STM. ARPES investigation reveals that graphene is now intrinsic in this condition with the Fermi level pinned at the Dirac point. All these changes produce defects in the graphene layer, as well evident in the Raman spectra of the samples annealed at 450 °C and 650 °C where a well evident D peak develops. Interestingly, these defects can be healed by a further annealing at 800 °C. Indeed, in this case the Raman spectrum of the sample is characterized by the absence of the D peak due to defects, and also the I_{2D}/I_G ratio increases up to the same values found in the pristine graphene, indicating that the pristine (or better) graphene quality has been restored by the high

temperature process. This defect healing process is accomplished by a further evolution of the Ge surface underneath the graphene detected by STM, that now is 1x1 reconstructed, while graphene appears n-doped during ARPES measurements.

Thus we proved that post-growth annealing can tune the interface properties of the system in terms of doping and Ge surface reconstruction, and significantly are able to restore high quality graphene by healing the defects induced by hydrogen desorption.

Acknowledgements

This research has been supported by the projects “GdR 2020” A0375-2020-36566 by Lazio Innova and CALIPSOplus (GA 730872 EU HORIZON 2020). We acknowledge Elettra Sincrotrone Trieste for access to its synchrotron radiation facilities and the the SGM-3 beamline of the synchrotron ASTRID-2 (Denmark) for the ARPES measurements.

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Fig. 1 Samples grown at different T_D . (a): Raman spectra. (b-d): AFM (upper panels) and STM (lower panels) images

Fig. 2. Samples grown at 930 °C and annealed at different temperature T . Right panel: Raman spectra. Left lower panels:

STM measured at 10 K; left upper panels: ARPES measurements.